

Elements to support regional (i.e., sub-national) bioeconomy development

Insights from in-depth analysis carried out by the ShapingBio project indicate that besides the efforts at national level, fostering regional bioeconomy development requires actions across different interconnected areas, including:

These elements are interlinked and can mutually influence one another, making it essential to account for regional specificities and characteristics.

This results will be verified with policy makers and other stakeholder groups.

About

SHAPINGBIO

ShapingBio

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ShapingBio is an EU-funded project with the overall aim to support and accelerate bioeconomy innovation and the deployment of new knowledge in the EU and its member states.

ShapingBio aims to provide evidence-based and concrete information and recommendations for better policy alignment and stakeholder actions to realise the cross-sectoral potential of the bioeconomy and to reduce the fragmentation across biobased sectors and the food system, as well as in policies across regions, domains and governance levels.

www.shapingbio.eu

4 Interconnected Action Areas for fostering regional bioeconomy development

#1 Policy

- Identify regional strengths (e.g. in terms of available feedstock, waste streams, human capital, infrastructure and industrial landscape).
- Establish priorities and develop a region-specific vision that aligns with local characteristics, while ensuring coherence with national frameworks and policies.

#3 Finance

- Develop adaptive and streamlined funding mechanisms with support to business at all stages, from early R&D to market entry, simplify access, and align with regional strengths
- Enhance company support through structured partnerships, equity investment schemes, and milestone-based funding to support bioeconomy scaling and commercialisation.

#2 Collaboration

- Mobilise existing collaborative platforms to foster a climate for change in the region.
- Facilitate regional multi-stakeholder groups and cross-sectoral knowledge sharing.
- Create channels for inter-regional collaboration and knowledge exchange with other regions nationally and internationally.

#4 Community Engagement

- Maintain open and ongoing communication channels between regional stakeholders (e.g., local authorities, academics, NGOs and regional industry representatives) and local communities.
- Establish regional multi-actor collaborative frameworks and initiatives to empower residents and encourage active participation in bioeconomy activities.

Read the full deliverable: https://www.shapingbio.eu/media/5rkncm45/shapingbio_d2-1_policy-governance_final.pdf

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